

High-yielding and good-quality Tianjin 1244 japonica hybrid cultivar series

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Japonica rice hybrids have been studied and used for 40 years (Yang 1999). For a long time, researchers have always used yield improvement as a priority goal in developing japonica hybrids. Hybrid rice has nearly become synonymous with high yield, leaving quality behind. To breed a japonica hybrid cultivar with high yield and good quality, a japonica restorer line with good quality is needed. The restorer must be genetically different from the sterile line so that good quality and high heterosis can be combined. Tianjin 1244, bred by the TRRI in 1985, is a japonica restorer line with good quality (Niu et al 1988).

Tianjin 1244 was bred from the cross between female parent Honqi 8 (with good quality and resistance to rice blast) and restorer line C57-10 (with poor quality but strong resistance to drought). The F₁ obtained was crossed with japonica Chusheng, which has good quality and high yield. Tianjin 1244 was the result of several generations of selection. It has good quality, early maturity, flourishing growth, and loose panicles.

Results of a quality analysis done on Tianjin 1244 by the Crop Germplasm Institute (CGI) of the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences (CAAS) showed that the appearance, milling quality, and protein content of Tianjin 1244 are better than those of checks Zhongdan 2 and

Zhonghua 9. Its cooking quality is similar to that of checks and its taste is intermediate. Tianjin 1244 met the Chinese Ministry of Agriculture (CMA) standard for quality (Table 1).

Tianjin 1244 has excellent restoring ability from wide crosses with 15 japonica cytoplasmic male sterile lines from different regions. The six test-cross F₁s gave five lines with yields higher than that of the check Liyou 57 (6.3–59.6% range). F₁ seed setting ranged from 80.9% to 93.6% (Table 2). Jingyou 6 (Zhongzuo 59A/1244), bred by the Crop Research Institute of the Beijing Academy of Agriculture and Forest

Science, has good quality. The quality analyses made by CGI of CAAS and the China Rice Research Institute showed that mean values of all main characteristics (except for chalkiness, which is 15.3% higher) met the CMA standard. Moreover, Jingyou 6 has stable and high yield (yield higher than that of check Quiguang by 14.5–14.9%) and resistance to blast and green smut. It is being extensively released in Beijing, Tianjin, and Ningxia (Hong et al 1999).

An analysis of the appearance of 63 japonica hybrid combinations in 1999 showed that two parents with good quality

Table 1. Results of rice quality analysis.

Variety	Appearance		Milling quality			Nutritional quality			
	Translucency (%)	Chalkiness (%)	Brown rice (%)	Partially milled (%)	Fully milled (%)	Protein (%)	Lysine (%)	Gross fat (%)	Total starch (%)
Tianjin 1244	1	1	83.1	74.2	73.5	9.0	0.3	2.5	76.5
Zhonghua 9	3	5	81.5	62.7	54.6	7.9	0.3	2.7	74.2
Zhongdan 2	3	5	82.9	71.2	68.0	8.4	0.3	2.2	73.6

Variety	Cooking quality			Eating quality ^a			
	Amylose (%)	Gel consistency	Gelatinization temperature	Eating	Color	Flavor	General evaluation
Tianjin 1244	16.6	Soft	Low	8.4	8.7	8.3	34.0
Zhonghua 9	18.2	Soft	Low	8.8	8.8	8.7	34.8
Zhongdan 2	16.2	Soft	Low	8.1	8.3	8.4	33.1

^aMaximum value is 10; the higher the rating, the better.

Table 2. F₁ generation obtained from cross combinations with Tianjin 1244.

Combination	Plant height (cm)	Panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Seed setting (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹) (%)	Increase over	
								Check 1 (%)	Check 2 (%)
Hong 12A/Tianjin 1244	106.5	15.6	23.6	186.2	84.2	26.9	16.4	+68.2	+59.6
Hong 21A/Tianjin 1244	108.1	14.6	20.5	139.2	88.7	25.9	11.7	+19.8	+13.9
Hong 26A/Tianjin 1244	99.0	12.2	19.9	205.7	85.7	23.9	12.8	+31.4	+24.8
Liao 5A/Tianjin 1244	95.5	16.0	18.8	156.2	80.9	26.2	13.2	+35.2	+28.5
Nong 6A/Tianjin 1244	98.0	12.0	21.0	141.3	93.6	27.6	10.9	+12.0	+6.3
8436A/Tianjin 1244	101.0	11.4	19.8	115.9	90.3	27.0	–	–17.7	–21.8
Tianjin 1244 (check 1)	101.4	11.6	22.4	135.4	91.9	27.1	7.9		
Liyou 57 (check 2)	95.2	14.1	19.9	145.0	87.7	23.0	10.2		

had an F₁ with good quality. A japonica hybrid with good quality can be obtained by combining a sterile line with good quality and a restorer line with good quality. Combining different plant types and different panicle types will make the heterosis of F₁ more powerful.

References

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Yield potential of Brazilian upland rice

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Brazil is the only rice-growing country where upland and irrigated lowland rice are equally important. Upland rice area in the 1999-2000 crop season was 2.35 million ha, while lowland rice area was 1.21 million ha. Production from these two ecosystems totaled 4.44 and 6.34 million t, respectively, indicating that average rice yield under irrigated conditions is 177% higher (IBGE 2001).

Nevertheless, EMBRAPA's breeding program has emphasized exploitation of yield potential in upland rice germplasm, as well as improving grain quality and increasing blast resistance. Lately, this effort has paid off. Our objective is to show that the yield potential of upland rice breeding lines is much higher than the national average and higher than that of the most common upland varieties.

Breeding lines generated by the different breeding programs in Brazil are included in a set of common trials (observation, preliminary, and advanced yield) that are evaluated in the Brazilian Network for Rice Germplasm Evaluation (BNRGE). Trials are conducted in the most important upland rice-growing areas in the country. Each trial includes around 16 entries plus 4 checks.

Table 1 compares the mean yields of two elite lines and two widely planted varieties in the 1999-2000 cropping seasons. Under a wide range of environments, the new lines outyielded

the checks by 8–10%. Evaluation trials were conducted under the best soil and weather conditions. The elite breeding lines proved to be even better than the commercial varieties, resulting in 13–16% more yield under the same environment (Table 2). These results reveal not only the responsiveness of elite lines but also their ability to withstand adverse conditions.

The best breeding lines, under good experimental conditions, achieve

yields almost three times higher than the national average (1.9 t ha⁻¹). The release of new varieties, combined with better agricultural technologies that are already available, will increase the average yield of upland rice in Brazil in the short term.

Reference

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Table 1. Average yield (t ha⁻¹) of elite breeding lines (EL) and check varieties (CV) of upland rice evaluated in BNRGE, 1999-2000.

Genotype	Type	1999	2000	Av	% increase over check
CNA8557	EL	3.6	3.9	3.8	110
CNA8540	EL	3.7	3.8	3.8	110
Primavera	CV	3.4	3.6	3.5	102
Caiapó	CV	3.4	3.4	3.4	100
Trial av		3.4	3.5	3.5	
Trials (no.)		51	66	117	

Table 2. Average yield (t ha⁻¹) of elite breeding lines (EL) and check varieties (CV) of upland rice evaluated in high-yield environments, BNRGE, 1999-2000.

Genotype	Type	1999	2000	Av	% increase over check
CNA8557	EL	5.4	5.3	5.3	116
CNA8540	EL	4.9	5.5	5.2	114
Primavera	CV	4.4	4.8	4.6	101
Caiapó	CV	4.5	4.7	4.6	100
Trial av		4.6	4.9	4.8	
Trials (no.)		20	22	42	